

ELEMENTARY STUDENTS PHYSICAL FEATURES OF THE TRAINING LESSON

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Annotation.

This article will introduce children of primary school age to a physical education lesson and further improve their health and health through various exercises. Formation of their conscious attitude towards physical education lessons in them.

Keywords.

healthy lifestyle, physical activity, musculoskeletal system, flat feet, personal hygiene, tasks for home

Relevance of the topic: each lesson in the science of Physical Culture should be focused on specific goals, have specific pedagogical tasks that determine the content of the lesson, methods of teaching and upbringing, selection of tools, ways of organizing the educational process. In the course of the lesson, it is necessary to form initial knowledge about the basics of Physical Culture and a healthy lifestyle in children. In the process of training, it is necessary that the teacher determines that the student is prone to certain types of sports and helps to practice these sports. Each lesson in the science of Physical Culture is connected in a logical sequence, it is necessary that a particular topic is aimed at mastering the educational material. It should be determined taking into account the size of the educational material, the stage of teaching exercise movements, positive and negative tolerance of exercises by students, readiness of students in the classroom, age characteristics. The most important requirement of a physical culture lesson - it is to ensure coordination and an individual approach, taking into account the health, gender, physical development, mobility, development characteristics of mental characteristics and qualities of students, compliance with hygiene standards. Primary school age (children) covers children ages 6-7 to 11 (grades I-IV). Speaking about the features of learning the movements of students of primary school age, the development of their physical abilities, it is necessary to separately mention the standard repetitive and variable exercises and methods. When students begin to reliably perform

acquired exercise movements, the standard repeated exercise method must give its place to the variable exercise method. A characteristic feature of younger students is their great desire, interest, physical activity, high emotionality during class. Therefore, in the classroom, it is necessary to organize a rational discipline based on the clear implementation of the teacher's orders, instructions, to ensure freedom and independence of movement in students, to introduce tasks that stimulate creativity and initiative. The primary school age Control and assessment system is used to encourage the student's desire to develop personally and physically, improve results, increase activity, rejoice in physical exercise. Difficult instructions, monotonous tasks should be avoided when organizing classes with younger students. For children's games and training with an object, it is necessary to choose large and bright things (cubes, balls), taking into account their own characteristics of their visual imagination.

Primary school age is one of the most important periods in the growth and development of the body. From 5-7 to 10-11 years old, the length of the limbs increases rapidly, exceeding the growth rate of the body. The increase in body weight lags behind the growth rate of body length. Children's bones and skeletal muscles are high in organic matter and water, but low in minerals. A slight stretching of the musculoskeletal system will provide the child with a pronounced elasticity, but will not be able to create a strong "muscle corset" to maintain the normal location of the bones. As a result, deformation of the skeleton, the development of asymmetry of the body and limbs, the appearance of flat feet is possible. This requires special attention to the organization of the normal state of children and the use of physical activity.

1. For the primary school age, the leading tasks in the lesson are the tasks of improving natural movement movements (walking, running, jumping, throwing, climbing, etc.).

2. In one lesson, it is advisable to solve no more than 2-3 tasks related to mastering or improving educational material.

3. The younger the class, the more attention is paid to strengthening the leg muscles and forming the correct posture.

4. Outdoor games are required in each class. The game material should occupy half of the total time spent with children under 10-11 years old.

5. When teaching students the main types of movement, great attention should be paid to performing the exercises correctly, as well as harmonizing the learning process with the development of qualities of movement. In children, the ability to

memorize movements increases rapidly between the ages of 7 and 12, and from the age of 13, the development of motor memory slows down a little.

Physical education of children cannot be fully carried out only in physical education lessons. Students are required to perform homework on Physical Culture. With the help of homework, the following educational tasks are solved:

- 1) increase the movement activity of children;
- 2) strengthening the main muscle groups;
- 3) formation of the correct posture;
- 4) preparation for the implementation of educational standards and program requirements

In summary, the conduct of physical education classes in children of primary school age - includes measures aimed at improving the physiological state of children and their physical development. In this case, the nature of the activities of the teacher and students is determined by the methods used in the lessons. A complex of methods will help to most successfully solve the planned educational tasks. As students gain knowledge and experience of movement, it is necessary to gradually apply elements of creative activity, and then practice more and more independently. By working at school, applying the basic principles of technology, we achieve significant positive results in the formation of the creative activity of younger students. The main goal of the discipline of physical education is based on the formation of the student's views on individual and collective labor, the development of his attitude to his own health. 1. For the primary school age, the leading tasks in the lesson are the tasks of improving natural movement movements (walking, running, jumping, throwing, climbing, etc.).

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REFERENCES:

1. Ruzmatovich U. S. et al. INCREASING THE ACTIVITY OF SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN // World Bulletin of Social Sciences. - 2022. - T. 8. - C. 49-51.
2. Shahbazova G. Physical Culture Of Preschool Children // Journal of Academic Leadership. - 2022. - T. 21. - №. 1.
3. Gulrukh, S. (2022). CONDITIONS AND METHODS OF TEACHING THE THEORY OF MOVEMENT GAMES AND SPORTS ELEMENTS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENCE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(09), 75-84.
4. Shahbazova, G., & Usmanov, A. (2023). Conditions and Methods of Teaching the Theory of Movement Games and Sports Elements, Taking into Account the Development of Independence of Preschool Children. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(3), 119-123.
5. Shakhbazova, G. (2023). The Importance of Physical Education in the Health and Normal Development of Preschool Educational Institution Students. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(3), 124-129.

6. Tillayev, S., & Shahbazova, G. (2023). Methodology of Teaching the Basic Principles of Modern Table Tennis. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 166-171.

7. Shaxbazova, G. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING MUSTAQILLIGINI OSHIRISHNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA HARAKATLI O'YINLARNI O'RGATISH SHARTLARI VA USULLARI. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 81-86.

8. Gulrukh, S. (2022). METHODS OF ADAPTING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO SPORTS GAMES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 89-95.

9. Shahbazova, G. (2022). General hardening of children. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 46-50.

10. Shahbazova, G., & Alisher, U. (2022). The Importance Of Water Hardening Of Preschool Children. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 41-45.

11. Sattorovich, Y. G. U., & Tursunaliyevich, F. I. (2023). History of the Sport of Kurash. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(1), 329-333.

12. Yormatov, G. (2022). STOL TENNIS BILAN SHUG 'ULLANUVCHILARNING PSIXOLOGIK PEDAGOGIK MAHORATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 167-171.

13. G'ulomjon, Y. (2023). Metho Yormatov, G. S. (2020). CHANGES IN THE RESPIRATORY AND BLOOD SYSTEM AS A RESULT OF PHYSICAL EXERCISES. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(10), 130-133. *dological Principles of Development of Physical Quality of Endurance in Children and Adolescents. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 178-182.

14. Yormatov, G. S. (2020). CHANGES IN THE RESPIRATORY AND BLOOD SYSTEM AS A RESULT OF PHYSICAL EXERCISES. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(10), 130-133.

15. Sattorovich, Y. G. U., & Tursunaliyevich, F. I. (2023). Mass Sport Movement in Uzbekistan and its Role in Forming a Healthy Lifestyle. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(1), 334-337.

16. Yigitalievch, E. A. (2021). The role and importance of physical education and sports in the health of the harmoniously developed generation. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 2(10), 52-56.

17. Tursunaliyevich, F. I., & Omonboyvich, T. S. (2022). BASKETBOLCHILAR SPORT TRENIROVKASINING ASOSLARI. Ta'lim fidoyilari, 8, 91-96.

18. Abdukarimovich, M. A. STEPS OF DEVELOPMENT IN THE FORMATION OF THE STUDENT PERSONALITY. ЎЗБЕКИСТОНИНИҲ УМИДЛИ ЁШЛАРИ, 55.

19. Matluba M. The Role of Effective Use of Information Technologies in Teaching Natural Sciences //International Journal of Culture and Modernity. - 2022. - T. 14. - C. 82-85.

20. Abduxalilovna M. M. The internal miracle of the body is the blood //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. - 2022. - T. 11. - №. 05. - C. 71-74.

21. Abduxalilovna M. M. et al. MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI NOTOG'RI OVQATLANISHI NATIJASIDA MIKROELEMENTLAR YETISHMOVCHILIGI ASOSIDA KELIB CHIQUADIGAN TURLI HOLATLAR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. - 2022. - T. 25. - C. 27-30.

22. Abdukhalilovna M. M. THE IMPORTANCE OF IRON-RICH PRODUCTS IN THE PREVENTION OF ANEMIA COMPLICATIONS //Gospodarka i Innowacje. - 2022. - T. 24. - C. 989-992.

23. Ruzmatovich U. S. et al. INCREASING THE ACTIVITY OF SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. - 2022. - T. 8. - C. 49-51.

24. Shahbazova G. Physical Culture Of Preschool Children //Journal of Academic Leadership. - 2022. - T. 21. - №. 1.

25. Gulrukh, S. (2022). CONDITIONS AND METHODS OF TEACHING THE THEORY OF MOVEMENT GAMES AND SPORTS ELEMENTS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENCE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(09), 75-84.

26. Shahbazova, G., & Usmanov, A. (2023). Conditions and Methods of Teaching the Theory of Movement Games and Sports Elements, Taking into Account the Development of Independence of Preschool Children. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(3), 119-123.

27. Shakhbazova, G. (2023). The Importance of Physical Education in the Health and Normal Development of Preschool Educational Institution Students. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(3), 124-129.

28. Tillayev, S., & Shahbazova, G. (2023). Methodology of Teaching the Basic Principles of Modern Table Tennis. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 166-171.

29. Shaxbazova, G. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING MUSTAQILLIGINI OSHIRISHNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA HARAKATLI O'YINLARNI O'RGATISH SHARTLARI VA USULLARI. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 81-86.

30. Gulrukh, S. (2022). METHODS OF ADAPTING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO SPORTS GAMES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 89-95.

31. Shahbazova, G. (2022). General hardening of children. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 46-50.

32. Shahbazova, G., & Alisher, U. (2022). The Importance Of Water Hardening Of Preschool Children. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 41-45.